

ONE4ALL PROJECT

KICK OFF MEETING AND PRESENTATION OF CONSORTIUM

ONE4ALL project, financed under the Horizon Europe programme, **aims to boost manufacturing plants' transformation**, especially SMEs, towards industry 5.0, reinforcing their resilience under unexpected changes in social needs.

The strategy will deal with the development of plug-and-produce reconfigurable cyber-physical production modules: **self-reconfigurable mobile collaborative robots embedded with IIOT devices** for real-time monitoring and interconnectivity. The cobots and the embedded software will be replicated digitally through data-driven digital twins and controlled by a self-learning AI-based distributed and multidisciplinary decision support system.

In addition, an adaptive training programme for digital upskilling will be implemented over the entire project to prepare the workforce for the I5.0 transformation and fully exploit the potential of the technologies.

The potential of ONE4ALL will be demonstrated in two relevant environments from different sectors (agri-food and pharmaceutical), both highly affected by disruption given their high and fluctuant demand.

The members of the Consortium met for the first time on 2nd and 3rd February 2023 in Seville, for the official Kick-off Meeting of the project: partners have discussed the next steps and activities, the responsibilities of each partner, the monitoring and reporting tools.

Figure 1: One4all Consortium during Kick-off meeting in Seville

The meeting was held in Spain, in the city where the headquarters of the Project Coordinator is located: **IDENER** is a private research SME, born as a spin-off of the University of Seville, in charge of project management and of the technical task for the development of the Intelligent Orchestration Platform.

EXELISIS is a Greek engineer-based consultancy company with extensive experience in business development and innovation especially emphasizing in the materials and energy field; they are leader of WP6 – Dissemination, communication and exploitation, and in charge of activities related to exploitation, replicability and innovation management.

CRIT is a company specializing in technical-scientific information research and analysis; it will oversee technology scouting, management of WP5 – Demonstration activities and evaluation, communication and dissemination of results, and standardisation activities. The company is located in Italy, as well as Automationware and Madama Oliva.

Automationware is specialised in disruptive innovation, technology, research applied to mechatronics and robotics; in the project, it will be responsible for the design, development and integration of collaborative robots in the demo-cases.

Madama Oliva, a family-owned company supplier of fresh table olives and derived products, will be the first demonstrator factory of One4all project.

The second demonstrator will be **Orifarm** (in specific, the premises located in the Czech Republic), an international supplier of pharmaceutical products.

3 universities will be involved in the activities of One4all project:

- **Karlsruhe Institute of Technology** in Germany will lead WP2 – Data Driven Digital Twins and distributed decision support system.
- **University of Southern Denmark** will ensure the development of a secure digital tools and the cyber security of the intelligent orchestration platform.
- **TU Dortmund University** in Germany will be responsible for the assessment of workforce digital maturity, work safety, development and implementation of training programmes.

Innglobal is an Irish organisation of experts in the field of education, technology and digital culture. They will be responsible for WP1 – Human and sustainability impact assessment.

Finally, **Holoss** is a Portuguese company committed to transforming society into greener and healthier by working with holistic, sustainable, respectful, and balanced business models. In One4all they will develop the lifecycle sustainability assessment tools and methodologies.

[Want to know more about the project?](#)

More details on the project activities, results, consortium are available on the official website: <https://one4allproject.eu/>

To remain updated, follow One4all social medias: [LinkedIn](#) and [Twitter](#)